

The Gendered Voices of Voice Assistants

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***Abstract:** The advancements in artificial intelligence, genetic engineering, and neural networks have created a paradigm shift in the inner consciousness of the humans across the world. The man machine assemblage has obfuscated the boundaries between human and machine. The gendered notions of the society are being replicated in the cyberspace as well. This is conspicuous in the case of Google assistants or bots and the first modern digital virtual assistant launched in 2011 initially, have taken up an inevitable role in the daily lives of people. Google, Apple's Siri, Amazon's Alexa, and Microsoft's Cortana are some of the widespread voice assistants. Female assistants and their voices are used by default which reinforces gender bias in the cyber world. Many companies attempt to offer multiple voices including those of celebrities, and popular characters, people tend to use the voice of the female. These zeroes in the stereotyping role of considering females in the servile position underpinning the patriarchal ideology of female for service and male for authority. Gender neutral voice assistants like Q which was launched in 2019 are still unpopular and was not widely acknowledged into the public domain. This paper attempts to study the gendered notions of voice assistants and how gender neutral assistants like Q try to subvert the female voice assistants by adapting an all-inclusive strategy.*

Keywords: Consciousness, Gender neutral, Voice assistants, Artificial intelligence, Cyberspace

Compared to earlier life, humans rarely get a chance to live outside technology and today's advanced technological era gives hardly a human activity without technology. There has been a cultural shift with the introduction of techno mediated activities and women get opportunities in the digital space to record their opinions. This allows them to construct their own spaces in technological phase narrating their exclusive experiences and stories and taking their own freedom to indulge in various activities. Gendered identities become contested terrains and what it is to become man or woman is no longer defined by the biological determinism but provides diverse ways of becoming. At one hand, gender is liberating in the fast moving technological era, where virtual space offers a new platform to move beyond the cultural and social relations and the conventional patterns of gender roles. It connects women globally through web and provides opportunities for women where their voices become heard and visible. The new biomedical technologies offer bodily transformations where new models of profiling individuals allow unprecedented ways of reconsidering what it means to be human. World Wide Web provides equal grounding especially for women and the marginalised where they actively engage with the technological phase undermining the social constructs of society. The advancements in artificial intelligence, genetic engineering and neural networks have created a paradigm shift in the inner consciousness of the humans across the world. The posthuman phase clearly delineates the shadowy lines among the humans, machine, animals and the environment. The anthropocentric views are reconfigured in the posthuman phase where humans are no

longer considered as a monolithic entity whose autonomous features have been glorified hitherto.

The corporate culture is created by men and they dominate the technological phase creating programs according to their ideologies. Technology has become ubiquitous in human life and according to Donna Haraway we are in the process of becoming cyborgs (150). In the post pandemic phase most of the people tend to use cyberspace more often for official as well as entertainment purposes. This has become a necessity in people's lives as we are bombarded constantly with techno scientific developments. There are many instances in the digital domain where technology mirrors and replicates cultural as well as social implications of society. Even though the liberation aspects persist, technology seems to be male dominated and women consider the virtual or digital domain as possible spaces where they can reconstruct their ideas and notions. It is quite evident that the society's patriarchal culture has been replicated in the cyberspace as well. Even in the 21st century with all these progressive thoughts and innovations we cannot deny the fact that the patriarchal structure has been completely expunged from the digital domains. The inherent philosophical patterns of male domination are still followed across the world especially when women are always considered as subversive.

This deep rooted ideology is reflected in arts, popular culture, films and the cultural terrains and throughout the ages feminists have fought for their space and equal rights. The fourth wave feminism zeroed in the problems women face in the internet, especially social media. Women got ample space to open up about sensitive topics on their own through social media considering it as an effective platform to share their experiences across the world. Without being judgmental and even without revealing their original identity, hiding their physical appearances, women can use

these platforms to create their own discourses and share their notions globally. Women writers too made use of the cyberspace to pen their experiences and enrich their creativity. They wrote narratives including characters of cyborgs and robots as tools which is constructed in their imaginative liberated space. Cyborgs reject the rigid boundaries which separates man from woman and human from machine. But there are evidences of patriarchal framework in the cyberspace too. Let us consider the case of Virtual Google Assistants, the first modern digital virtual assistant Apple's Siri was launched in 2011. Siri marked ground-breaking step in building personal assistants allowing users to interact with them using natural voice language. Siri is designed to assist humans in helping out in all possible ways by performing various tasks like searching the internet, making calls, sending messages, providing directions, and setting reminders and so on. Following Siri, other major virtual assistants like Google Assistant, Amazon's Alexa and Microsoft's Cortana followed and are popular among the public. These virtual assistants use artificial intelligence and natural language processed to understand and respond to user's request, serving as invaluable tools in everyday life. The specific duties of a voice assistant differ according to the need and demand of the clients and institutions. Virtual assistants continue to evolve and go through upgradations synthesising with smart home devices and offering varying applications to support users across many years with efficiency and convenience.

“The AI assistant understands natural language voice commands and completes tasks for the user. Such tasks historically performed by a personal assistant or secretary include taking dictation, reading text or email messages aloud, looking up phone numbers, scheduling, placing phone calls, playing songs and reminding the end user about appointments” (“AI Assistant”). All

these devices have female assistants by default which reinforces gender bias in the cyber world. People consider the voice of women more warm, soothing, and easy to trust too. Even though many companies offer multiple voices including those of celebrities, and other characters, people tend to follow the voice of the female. The justification regarding the allegation is given by the companies is that women's sound is more suitable for voice production due to the increase in pitch. "The UNESCO had released a report about "gender bias in the field of artificial intelligence, arguing that voice assistants are inflaming gender stereotypes and teaching sexism by creating a model of "docile and eager-to-please helpers," programmed to be submissive and accept verbal abuse" (UNESCO, I'd Blush If I Could).

AI can bring more efficient, smarter and cost effective innovations in our daily work life. But more inclusive AI bots are necessary to think from an alternative perspective and for dismantling the stereotypical gendered positions of the society. "Because the speech of most voice assistants is female, it sends a signal that women are available at the touch of a button or with a blunt voice command like 'hey' or 'OK,'" (UNESCO, I'd Blush If I Could). This feminization of digital labour replicates and reiterates the gender stereotypes in social imaginary and expectations. These female assistants are preprogrammed to be submissive and compliant accepting verbal commands and abuse.

The Silicon Valley culture and the male corporates create technology according to their own ideologies and people who lead, aim at projecting gendered discourses in the digital space. The female voice in these Google assistants maybe due to the fact that women are always underrepresented in the technological industry. The society is conditioned in a patriarchal pattern considering female voices as obedient or more servile to make comfortable

commands towards them. Many tones or commands given by users won't be addressed by the assistants and they become silent or less responsive to yelling and abuse. This indeed gives a negative impact to the future generations that women are supposed to take up verbal abuses silently or women shouldn't react to such abuses. Miriam Vogel, executive director of Equal AI says, "We're teaching our next generation to double down on those stereotypes" (Giacobbe). The names given to these devices also replicate feminine features.

Many girls have encountered relentless bullying with the name Alexa in schools as they share their names with the AI Alexa. The bullying involves peer students shouting and giving commands to the girls, ostracization, and harassment like people do with the voice assistants. As per many reports this has taken a toll in the mental health of girls leading to change the names of some girls. Some parents have filed a complaint showing that their daughter was bullied by her friends and ordered her tasks to do. They have requested Amazon to consider changing the Google assistant's name. So it is evident that how children perceive aspects about these digital devices as someone who obeys them at the same time remaining submissive. This issue bothers worldwide and Amazon has expressed concerns over these families. These incidents show unintended adverse effects in the social domains and experts say more ethical consideration is needed in choosing AI names.

A group of researchers, sound designers and linguists teamed up with the organisers of Copenhagen Pride in 2019 in association with technology leaders. Equal AI launched a unique, gender neutral voice assistant called Q or Quinn. They recorded and collected several sample voices of people which include male, female, transgender or nonbinary. "One of our big goals with Q

was to contribute to a global conversation about gender, and about gender and technology and ethics, and how to be inclusive for people that identify in all sorts of different ways," says Julie Carpenter, a professional in human behaviour and emerging technologies who worked on developing Project Q(npr.org). So this initiative is a huge shift in the field of cyberspace which challenges the gendered stereotyping of voice assistants adapting an all-inclusive strategy. Q subverts the idea of a gendered notion of society and offers an alternate system that would surely help to wipe off the gender bias which still exists in our society. They presume that more people in future would opt for gender neutral assistants and this would become the future of voice assistants. Project Q aims at developing and implementing androgynous tone that users of all genders feel comfortable. This fosters a gender inclusive strategy and takes a leap towards gender ethics and inclusivity in the emerging technology.

Works Cited

"Apple Eliminates Gender Bias, Introduces Two New Voices to Its Virtual Assistant Siri." Zee News, 17 Jan. 2023, www.zeenews.india.com/technology/apple-eliminates-gender-bias-introduces-two-new-voices-to-its-virtual-assistant-siri-2352133.html.

Felten, Ed. "How AI Bots and Voice Assistants Reinforce Gender Bias." Brookings, 15 July 2020, <https://www.brookings.edu/research/how-ai-bots-and-voice-assistants-reinforce-gender-bias/>.

"Female by Default - Exploring the Effect of Voice Assistant Gender and Pitch on Trait and Trust Attribution." ResearchGate, 2021, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351427517_Fema

le_by_Default__Exploring_the_Effect_of_Voice_Assistant
_Gender_and_Pitch_on_Trait_and_Trus Attribution

Giacobbe, Alyssa. "The Gender Bias Behind Voice Assistants." *Architectural Digest*, 5 Nov. 2019, <https://www.architecturaldigest.com/story/the-gender-bias-behind-voice-assistants>.

Gillespie, Patrick. "Meet Q, the Gender-Neutral Voice Assistant." *NPR*, 21 Mar, 2019, <https://www.npr.org/2019/03/21/705395100/meet-q-the-gender-neutral-voice-assistant>

Haraway, Donna. "A Cyborg Manifesto: Science, Technology, and Socialist-Feminism in the Late Twentieth Century." *Simians, Cyborgs and Women: The Reinvention of Nature*, Routledge, 1991, pp. 149-181.

Lunden, Ingrid. "Siri Gains a New Gender-Neutral Voice Option in Latest iOS Update." *TechCrunch*, 24 Feb. 2022, <https://techcrunch.com/2022/02/24/siri-gains-a-new-gender-neutral-voice-option-in-latest-ios-update/>.

"We Weren't Being Sexist Giving Assistant a Female Voice." *Futurism*, 18 Sept. 2019, <https://futurism.com/the-byte/google-assistant-female-voice>.

United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. *I'd Blush If I Could: Closing Gender Divides in Digital Skills through Education*. UNESCO, 2019. unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000367416.